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Research Article

**PREDICTIVE VALUE OF Q WAVES IN INFERIOR LEADS FOR
THE DIAGNOSIS OF OLD INFERIOR WALL MYOCARDIAL
INFARCTION (IMI)**¹Dr.Muhammad Sabir Raza, ²Dr.Ammara Akbar, ³Dr.Shireen Khan¹FMH College OF Medicine and Dentistry,Lahore, ²Aziz Fatima Medical and Dental College Faisalabad, ³Foundation University Medical College.**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

Background- The diagnosis of IMI on a regular performed ECG can lead to further imaging studies and consultation. The objective of this study is to examine both repolarization abnormalities and Q waves in inferior leads or only Q waves in inferior leads in IMI diagnosis through imaging studies.

Methods- In this study all those 56 patients were included inferior wall myocardial infarction was diagnosed during computerized interpretation of ECG and imaging studies. The GE MAC-HD 5500 was used to perform ECG. MUSE GE system was used to interpret the Electrocardiograms. Using Standard techniques and equipment nuclear medicine cardiac imaging and ECG were interpreted and performed. To calculate binomial confidence interval(CI) SAS 9.3 software was used.

Results- IMI was diagnosed during the computerized interpretation of Electrocardiograms when these were compared with confirmed IMI imaging studies, and the this had 52.7% positive predictive value. This positive predictive value was increased up to 80% when wider Q waves criteria than 0.04ms was added during ECG interpretation. Also, this positive predictive value was increased up to 92% in the presence of isoelectric or negative T waves and ST changes.

Conclusion- "These results suggest that the computerized interpretation of ECG results in a high rate of false positive readings of old inferior myocardial infarction. This may result in over-utilization of imaging modalities. Presence of diagnostic Q waves in inferior leads, if accompanied by repolarization abnormalities, improves the accuracy of the electrocardiogram for the diagnosis of inferior wall myocardial infarction."

Keywords: Electrocardiograms, Q waves, Myocardial infarction

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INTRODUCTION:

The diagnosis of IMI on a regular performed ECG can lead to further imaging studies, psychological stress, additional costs and consultation for patients. According to “The Third Global MI Task Force” below given finding in ECG can be an indication of prior IMI.

- Pathological findings of IMI. Diagnosis, classification, and treatment of acute myocardial infarction is based on biomarker findings and electrocardiographic.
- Imaging evidence of a region of loss viable myocardium that is thinned and fails to contract, in the absence of a non-ischemic cause
- Pathological Q waves with or without symptoms in the absence of non- ischemic causes

Normally the amplitude and duration of Q waves is used to diagnose new or old IMI. If these Q waves have depth greater than -0.2mV and are wider than 40ms then it is considered as pathological. However, despite of reliance on the findings of ECG there have been lack of literature and research to examine the Q waves in inferior leads in IMI diagnosis through imaging studies. The objective of this study is to examine both repolarization abnormalities and Q waves in inferior leads or only Q waves in inferior leads in IMI diagnosis through imaging studies.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was conducted in Department of Medicine in Fatima Memorial Hospital Lahore. Where 2500 routinely performed ECG, were read and out of these in 135 ECG IMI was diagnosed as shown in below figure 1.

Figure 1: Findings of abnormal electrocardiograms and cardiac imaging studies

In this study all those 56 patients were included inferior wall myocardial infarction was diagnosed during computerized interpretation of ECG and imaging studies. The GE MAC-HD 5500 was used to perform ECG. MUSE GE system was used to interpret the Electrocardiograms. Using Standard techniques and equipment nuclear medicine cardiac imaging and ECG were interpreted and performed.

Normally the amplitude and duration of Q waves is used to diagnose new or old IMI. If these Q waves have depth greater than -0.2mV and are wider than 40ms then it is considered as pathological.

Echocardiograms were analyzed for the presence or absence of inferior wall motion abnormalities and wall thickness. Cardiac scintigraphic images were analyzed for inferior wall fixed perfusion defects and

coronary angiograms were analyzed for occlusion of the right coronary artery accompanied by angiographic evidence of left ventricular inferior wall

motion abnormalities. To calculate binomial confidence interval(CI) SAS 9.3 software was used.

Table 1: Distribution of the patients with computer-generated diagnosis of inferior wall myocardial infarction and imaging studies.

		Echocardiogram or Nuclear Med Study		
		Positive	Negative	Total
ECG	Positive	19	17	36
	Negative	11	9	20
	Total	30	26	56

RESULTS:

IMI was diagnosed in 135 patients of Electrocardiograms with computer-generated in which 56 patients have diagnostic imaging studies, 30 of these have abnormal studies and yielding 53.6% PPV. These final selected patients have median age of 63 years and out of these 56, 38 were males.

s, 30 of these patients had abnormal studies, yielding a PPV of 53.57% (95% exact CI: 39.74%-67.01%). Among the 56 patients included in this study, the average age was 63 years, and 38 (67.8%) were male.

IMI was diagnosed during the computerized interpretation of Electrocardiograms when these were compared with confirmed IMI imaging studies, and

the this had 52.7% positive predictive value. Thirty-one electrocardiograms were identified fulfilling the abnormal Q wave criteria by the manual method. Some patients had abnormal Q waves without repolarization abnormalities (Figure 2). This positive predictive value was increased up to 80% when wider Q waves criteria than 0.04ms was added during ECG interpretation. In 25 patients, repolarization abnormalities, characterized by ST segment changes or T-wave inversions accompanying the abnormal Q waves in inferior leads were noted (Figure 3).

Also, this positive predictive value was increased up to 92% in the presence of isoelectric or negative T waves and ST changes.

Figure 2: Abnormal Q waves with T wave inversion.

Figure 3: Abnormal Q waves without T wave inversion.

DISCUSSION:

Normally the amplitude and duration of Q waves is used to diagnose new or old IMI. If these Q waves have depth greater than -0.2mV and are wider than 40ms then it is considered as pathological. However, despite of reliance on the findings of ECG there have been lack of literature and research to examine the Q waves in inferior leads in IMI diagnosis through imaging studies.

Modernized understanding of electrocardiogram, whenever joined by the conclusion of substandard divider myocardial localized necrosis, may prompt further assessment and imaging considers. Generally, there has been a helpless connection between's the PC created electrocardiographic finding of a mediocre divider myocardial dead tissue and the affirmed conclusion of a second-rate divider myocardial localized necrosis by imaging examines.

Deferred Enhancement Cardiac Magnetic Resonance (DE-CMR) is all around approved as a noninvasive reference standard for LV infarct evaluation. Be that as it may, the populace-based utilization of DE-CMR as an essential method for recognizing and delineating infarct weight would involve considerable expenses and won't be doable in numerous patients. Conversely, ECG is a reasonable and promptly accessible device.

There has all the earmarks of being a worldly decrease in the size of the Q waves after myocardial localized necrosis [9]. An examination between mid (4 ± 0.4 days after AMI) and later development (29 ± 6 days), ECG exhibited fleeting decreases in Q-wave adequacy. A 14 to 37% decrease in hyperimprovement size has been accounted for among right on time and subsequent DE-CMR. Pathologic Q waves are identified with the size of myocardial localized necrosis. Enormous myocardial areas of dead tissue, including over 10% of the left ventricular myocardium, are regularly joined by Q waves, while little infarcts can happen without pathologic Q waves on electrocardiogram. This may clarify the nonattendance of electrocardiographic determination of myocardial localized necrosis in patients who have a past filled with past myocardial dead tissue.

CONCLUSION:

These results suggest that the computerized interpretation of ECG results in a high rate of false positive readings of old inferior myocardial infarction. This may result in over-utilization of imaging modalities. Presence of diagnostic Q waves in inferior leads, if accompanied by repolarization abnormalities, improves the accuracy of the

electrocardiogram for the diagnosis of inferior wall myocardial infarction.

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